

Specific Features of Emotional - Expressivity of the Intonation

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Abstract: Descriptive phonetics considers speech sounds, their types of formation, changes, and phonetic phenomena such as syllables, intonation, pauses, accents, and features inherent in them. The missed events combine into a holistic system in the process of speech communication, giving rise to a single speech act. So the segment that forms the speech chain, supersegment elements participate in speech almost the same way.

Keywords: syllable, intonation, pause, accent, rhythm, speech process.

Emotive intonation is the zone of expressing emotions that can compound the emotive meanings of different language units. Darwin claimed that the expression of emotions involves many systems: facial expression, behavioral response, and physical responses, which include physiological, postural, and vocal changes. The rhythmic aspects of speech, including tempo and timing, contribute significantly to emotional prosody. Speaking at an accelerated tempo might convey enthusiasm or urgency, while a slower pace may signify contemplation or sadness. Emotional expression is part of the emotion regulation process and functions as a way to communicate internal states to others. Emotional expression can include behavioral, nonverbal, and/or verbal expressions. Emotional expression can be beneficial when adaptive and fit to a given situation. In expressive intonation sharps are played slightly higher and flats slightly flatter than they are on a keyboard. The cellist Pablo Casals is often credited with the coining of the term. It is widely supported within the scientific community that there are seven basic emotions, each with its own unique and distinctive facial expression. These seven are: happiness, sadness, fear, disgust, anger, contempt and surprise. Expressing emotions is more than just a simple act of communication. It's a powerful coping skill with wide-reaching benefits, transforming our personal understanding, stress management, social connections, and the way we interact with others. An example of a verbal emotional expression is identifying a feeling with words. Saying things like "I feel disappointed" or "I'm so excited!" Another example of how verbal emotional expression is used is a tone of voice. It is possible to identify emotions even when we do not know the language.

The role of supersegmented elements in expressing emotional-expressiveness is large. We will reflect on one of the supersegment phonetic tools intonation and its methodological features in this article. Intonation is a "Latin" word meaning to pronounce with a high tone, a tone. Intonation serves to express the syntactic meaning and emotional coloring of speech fragments. It is realized in speech through loudness, tone

Features characteristic of intonation V in Russian linguistics. A. Artyomov, I. A. Svetazarova, E.A. Brizgunova, N.V. Cheremisina, A.N. Vasileva, A.A. Machkova, A.K. Ceplitis, R.M. It is found in the scientific work of scientists such as Gaiduchik.

And in Uzbek linguistics, the features characteristic of intonation are A. GüloMOV, H. YolandeVA,

E.Sabrev, I.Hajjaliev, A.It is covered in detail in the scientific work of the khidarovs. Balsa, researcher who analyzed the features characteristic of yuldoshova intonation from the point of view of excretory phonetics

In his scientific work, A. Khaydarov reflects on the connotative representation of intonation. According to some linguists, intonation is characteristic of oral speech and forms a separate system. All of these are considered supersegment tools, as well as always living in the structure of speech, since speech melody and rhythm, speech speed and timbre, and logical stress, among others, are components of intonation. The speed of each segment of a sentence is different in different communicative (communication) types, since each sentence performs a certain function. Darak, interrogations and command sentences provide feedback. Exclamation sentences represent emosia. When expressing emotional-expressiveness, intonation has a special character, since it is the main and characteristic sign of any sentence. It participates as a separate unit in gap construction. Intonation serves two functions.

1. Emotional produces an emotional statement from unbounded statements, that is, any statement uttered by exclamation intonation becomes an emotional statement. For example: What wonderful weather!
2. Expresses the emotionality of the speaker.

Emotionality is also determined by the speed of the sentence. The speed of each segment of a sentence varies in different communicative types. In particular, the comb starts more slowly than the speed of the possessive sentence given at the beginning of the sentence, reaching the maximum level in the cross-section. Exclamation points, on the other hand, are pronounced with a loud sound, as they have an exciting sign. But the speed decreases. The tone of speech is a system of high or low pronunciation of words in a sentence. Therefore, the tone of interrogative sentences is fundamentally different from the tone of narrow sentences. Likewise, the interrogative sentence is pronounced continuously with respect to the command sentence. For example, *Why should it worry you? How about phoning them?*

Separated sentence fragments, exclamations, introductory words are separated by tone in oral speech, and in written speech are separated by appropriate punctuation marks. Perhaps, it will rain!

In this example, the Perhapsis introduction is pronounced with intonation in oral speech when separated by a comma in writing. In colloquial communication, two features of intonation also come true, that is, intonation acts as a way to establish communication and influence the listener. Since intonation manifests its character in the speech process, above all as a means of influence, the height of the sound is distinguished in this regard in terms of audibility. Methodically, however, intonation also serves as an informational function in addition to the influencing task. In particular, intonation changes provide information about the speaker's mental state. The emotionality aspect of intonation mainly represents a methodological meaning. Intonation is an important tool in giving a certain stylistic coloring to the speaker's speech.

Thus, intonation can be used in everyday speech to teran its content and further enhance its effectiveness, since with the change of intonation, different emotions of the speaker are expressed. Intonation is a supersegment phonetic phenomenon inherent mainly in oral speech, the components of which are pause, as well as the methodological features of accent, which we reflect on in our separate works.

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